

What's New at ENSEMBLE? | September's Edition | Newsletter

A Month of Progress and Collaboration

As cybercrime becomes more sophisticated and global, collaboration and innovation are our best tools. This past month, the ENSEMBLE project has taken significant steps in the fight against this threat, joining forces with a network of 45 security projects and participating in key international forums to share our expertise. In this edition, we show you how our strategy of collaboration and technological development is forging a more secure digital future for Europe.

From Lone Wolf to RaaS: How Ransomware Is Reshaping the Cybercrime Landscape

2nd October

In the latest blog post, Dr. [Francesco Zola](#) from [Vicomtech](#) explores how the [ENSEMBLE](#) Project is fighting the growing threat of ransomware.

Ransomware is no longer a simple digital prank. It has evolved into a sophisticated criminal business, with the Ransomware-as-a-Service (RaaS) model lowering the entry barrier for cybercriminals and enabling attacks on an unprecedented scale. This evolution has turned governments, hospitals, and other critical infrastructure into its primary targets.

[Learn more](#)

AI4SafeEurope Cluster Webinar

3rd September

The **AI4SafeEurope Cluster** brings together eight European projects that use artificial intelligence to tackle security challenges, from disinformation to cybercrime. Its goal is to create a more secure digital future through collaboration.

On September 10, 2025, as part of its work, the cluster organized a webinar focused on the challenge of fake news and its social impact. Experts discussed how to ethically use AI to counter disinformation.

[Learn more](#)

Strengthening Europe's Cybersecurity Defense Together

29th July

The article, written by Dr. [Bernhard Haslhofer](#) from [IKNAIO](#), highlights the fragmentation of cybersecurity in Europe, where highly specialized companies often work in isolation. The [ENSEMBLE](#) project aims to solve this by creating an integrated ecosystem where these tools can collaborate. This cooperation is crucial for strengthening Europe's digital sovereignty and reducing dependence on external providers.

To illustrate this approach, the article mentions several collaborating companies: [CFLW](#) from the Netherlands, with extensive experience in dark web investigations; [IKNAIO](#) from Austria, which specializes in crypto-asset analysis; and [Byron Labs](#) from Spain, which provides real-time threat intelligence. By uniting their knowledge, the project seeks to offer law enforcement agencies a more efficient and cost-effective suite of European solutions, aligned with the region's needs.

[Learn more](#)

NEW MEMBER OF THE

ENSEMBLE equips Law Enforcement Agencies with innovative, user-driven tools to fight cybercrime. By analysing investigation gaps and cybercriminal methods, it will create a Toolbox for advanced detection, analysis, and correlation of cybercrime data.

ENSEMBLE Joins the LEA Projects Cluster

3rd October

We are proud to announce that the [ENSEMBLE](#) project has joined the **LEA Projects Cluster**, a collaborative network led by [Privanova](#) that now has 45 members. This union reinforces our commitment to equipping law enforcement agencies with cutting-edge tools to combat cybercrime. The collaboration will allow us to share knowledge and best practices with other European security projects to develop an advanced Toolbox designed for the detection and analysis of cybercrime-related data.

[Learn more](#)

BONUS INSIGHT JUST FOR YOU

INTERPOL New Technology Forum 2025

The [Complexity Science Hub](#) (CSH) in Vienna hosted the **INTERPOL New Technology Forum 2025**, an event that brought together international experts from 38 countries to discuss using advanced technologies in law enforcement. Under the theme "Dealing with Volume and Complexity," the forum focused on helping investigators handle massive amounts of data, from encrypted networks to cryptocurrency transactions.

The forum highlighted the importance of complexity science in revealing patterns in these systems and providing new tools for law enforcement. Several members of the [ENSEMBLE](#) project, including [CFLW](#) , [Byron labs](#) and [IKNAIO](#) , participated in this important event, strengthening the collaboration between the project and the international cybersecurity community.

[Learn more](#)

We appreciate your interest in ENSEMBLE. Please feel free to share this newsletter with colleagues who may wish to follow our progress. More updates coming soon!